

1 *Short Communication*

2 **Screening alternative therapies to control Nosemosis type C in honey bee (*Apis***
3 ***mellifera iberiensis*) colonies.**

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15 **ABSTRACT**

16 Nosemosis type C caused by the microsporidium *Nosema ceranae* is one of the most
17 widespread of the adult honey bee diseases, and due to its detrimental effects on both
18 strength and productivity of honey bee colonies, an appropriate control of this disease
19 is advisable. Fumagillin is the only veterinary medicament recommended by the World
20 Organization for Animal Health (OIE) to suppress infections by *Nosema*, but the use of
21 this antibiotic is prohibited in the European Union and few alternatives are available at

22 present to control the disease. In the present study three therapeutic agents
23 (Nosestat®, Phenyl salicylate and Vitafeed Gold®) have been tested to control *N.*
24 *ceranae* infection in honey bee colonies, and have been compared to the use of
25 fumagillin. None of the products tested were effective against *Nosema* under our
26 experimental conditions. Low consumption of the different doses of treatments may
27 have had a strong influence on the results obtained, highlighting the importance of this
28 issue and emphasizing that this should be evaluated in studies to test therapeutic
29 treatments of honey bee colonies.

30 **KEYWORDS**

31 *Apis mellifera*; *Nosema ceranae*; treatments; colony strength; honey production

32

33 Honey bees are pollinating insects of tremendous economic and ecological
34 importance. Alterations in the health status of bees entails a reduction in the vitality,
35 productivity and pollinating capability, affecting thus the viability of beekeeping
36 activity and the biodiversity (Klein et al., 2007; Bradbear, 2009). Accordingly, the
37 treatment of infectious diseases is a key aspect in beekeeping in order to ensure that
38 bees fulfil their role as food producers (Botías et al., 2013), and as pollinators of
39 several crops and native plants.

40 Nosemosis are among the most prevalent diseases affecting honey bees today and they are
41 caused by two distinct species of single-cellular fungal microsporidian parasites, *Nosema apis*
42 and *Nosema ceranae*. Currently the only effective treatment for *N. apis* and *N. ceranae*
43 infection is fumagillin (Higes et al., 2011). However, prolonged fumagillin usage in apiculture
44 may contribute to these microsporidia developing resistance to this drug and as reported

45 recently, declining concentrations of this molecule may exacerbate *N. ceranae* infection rather
46 than suppress it (Huang et al., 2013). Furthermore, the use of this antibiotic is no longer
47 licensed in the majority of EU member states, yet there are currently few alternatives available
48 to control this disease. Given the deleterious consequences reported in honey bee colonies
49 infected by *N. ceranae* and the high prevalence of this microsporidium in some regions of the
50 world (Martín-Hernández et al., 2012; Martínez et al., 2012; Bollan et al., 2013; Higes et al.,
51 2013), it is imperative to find new treatments to control the rapid spread of this dangerous
52 illness, now known as nosemosis type C (Higes et al., 2010).

53 The aim of this study was to assess the effectiveness of three potential therapeutic agents in
54 the treatment of nosemosis, comparing their effect to that of fumagillin (Fumidil-B®), whose
55 effectiveness in controlling *N. apis* (Gregorc and Sulimanovic, 1996) and *N. ceranae* infection
56 (Williams et al., 2008; Higes et al., 2011) has been demonstrated previously. The therapeutic
57 agents evaluated were the veterinary medicinal product Nosestat® (a.m. iodine and formic
58 acid), the herbal preparation Vitafeed Gold® (a concentrated aqueous extract of sugar beet
59 *Beta vulgaris* cv. *altissima*) and finally, the intestinal antiseptic Phenyl Salicylate (2-
60 Hydroxybenzoic acid phenyl ester). The first two are products sold as veterinary treatments
61 against nosemosis, while the third has previously been reported to be effective in the control
62 of *Nosema* infection (White, 1919; Pernal and Melathopoulos, 2009).

63 To perform this field assay, 50 homogeneous colonies of *Apis mellifera iberiensis* were
64 monitored monthly in experimental apiaries located at the “Centro Apícola de Marchamalo”
65 (CAR), from November 2008 to October 2009. All the colonies were acquired from the same
66 professional beekeeper as nuclei (5 combs with worker bees and a queen) in April 2008, and
67 they were left to develop and adapt to the field conditions of the study until June 2008, when
68 they were introduced into the new hives. At the start of the study, none of the colonies
69 showed clinical signs of chalkbrood, nor of American or European foulbrood. Furthermore, the

70 absence of *V. destructor* was confirmed after examining the bees following OIE methods (OIE,
71 2008), and *Nosema* spp. were not detected in the colonies when bee samples ($n \geq 30$ foragers)
72 were analysed using a specific multiplex PCR (Martín-Hernández et al., 2012). The areas
73 surrounding the hives contained no genetically modified agricultural crops, and no insecticides
74 like fipronil or imidacloprid were in use. The colonies were placed close to another apiary
75 containing colonies naturally parasitized by *N. ceranae* and/or *N. apis*, which acted as a natural
76 source of infection. *V. destructor* parasitization was controlled twice a year (Apivar® a.m.
77 amitraz) to avoid the negative effects of this parasite on colony health.

78 Once *N. ceranae* was detected in all 50 colonies by PCR (Martín-Hernández et al., 2012), in
79 November 2008, they were randomly assigned to 5 experimental groups containing 10
80 colonies each. These colonies were distributed in two different apiaries to reduce the risk of
81 reinfection of the treated colonies with *Nosema* spp. through contact with the untreated ones.
82 Both apiaries were situated 450 m apart and at a similar altitude (Apiary 1: 723 meters; Apiary
83 2: 700 meters), and they were surrounded by the same type of flora (degradation stage of
84 holm oak-Aleppo pine forest surrounded by cereal crops). In Apiary 1 (40°41'00.05''N,
85 3°12'54.63''W), 4 experimental groups were treated for infection with *Nosema* spp. as
86 described in Table 1, whereas 10 control colonies received one application of sugar syrup
87 (vehicle; 1:1 distilled water-sugar) in Apiary 2 (untreated colonies; 40°40'54.35''N,
88 3°12'34.88''W).

89 Fumidil-B®, Nosestat®, Phenyl Salicylate and sugar syrup was applied in plastic bags placed
90 over the brood chamber and their consumption was assessed weekly (Higes et al., 2011). On
91 the day that a new dose was administered, the remaining unconsumed doses were removed
92 from the colony and weighed. By contrast, Vitafeed Gold® was applied by dribbling it evenly
93 between the bee spaces, as recommended by the manufacturer. As such, the consumption of
94 this product could not be estimated.

95 From June 2008 until October 2009, clinical signs of pathologies other than Nosemosis, the
96 presence of a queen and colony mortality were recorded on each visit to the apiaries.

97 To evaluate the presence of *Nosema* spp. in the colonies, samples of forager bees ($n \geq 50$ bees)
98 were collected at noon, as described elsewhere (Meana et al., 2010). Forager bee samples
99 were collected before the application of the treatments and once the last dose was consumed,
100 the presence of *Nosema* spp. in the composite samples was analysed using methods described
101 previously (Martín-Hernández et al., 2012). This procedure was performed both in autumn
102 2008 and in spring 2009.

103 The adult bee population and brood production (i.e. uncapped and capped brood) were
104 evaluated each month throughout the assay (from December 2008 to October 2009, except in
105 August 2009), producing a total of 10 measurements. In each case the frames covered by bees
106 were analysed and the number of brood cells quantified (Botías et al., 2012a).

107 The honey produced by each colony was evaluated in the harvesting season (September 2009),
108 separately weighing all the frames with honey from each colony, and calculating the total
109 amount of honey stored in them from the difference in comb weight before and after honey
110 extraction (Botías et al., 2012a).

111 As for the statistical analysis, the dependent variables studied and normalized by linear
112 transformation were: adult honey bee population, number of brood cells and honey
113 production. Two factors were taken into account, one fixed factor (group) and the time effect.
114 We ran Generalized Estimation Equations with a normal probability distribution, identity as the
115 link function, colony as the subject effect and the time point as the within-subject effect.

116 Since the presence of interactions in the model revealed that the effects of interventions
117 varied with time, the mean values of the different parameters (adult honey bee population
118 and number of brood cells) were compared per group and time point using a one-way analysis
119 of variance (ANOVA). Where necessary, ANOVA was followed by Bonferroni or Tamhane post

120 hoc tests, depending on the homogeneity of variance in each case (determined using Levene's
121 test). In the case of honey production, as the sample size was small and the distribution of the
122 data was not normal, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare the mean
123 values recorded from each group in the harvesting season (September 2009), and a Mann-
124 Whitney test was used to compare between groups. All the analyses were carried out using
125 SPSS 18.0 software and in all the studies, differences were considered significant when $\alpha \leq$
126 0.05.

127 The results showed that the 50 composite forager bee samples analyzed all tested positive for
128 *N. ceranae* infection at the beginning of the assay in November 2008. After application of the
129 different products in late November 2008, all the colonies remained infected by this
130 microsporidium. Poor consumption of the treatments applied was observed (Table 2), except
131 in the case of Vitafeed Gold® whose consumption could not be assessed due to the method of
132 application (see above).

133 Larger amounts of the treatments applied in spring 2009 were consumed (Table 2), although
134 when forager bee samples were analysed after treatment, *N. ceranae* was still detected in all
135 the colonies studied. In this period, all the colonies showed the presence of *N. ceranae* and
136 one colony of those treated with NOS (Nosestat®), SAL (Phenyl Salicylate) and VIT (Vitafeed
137 Gold®) was also positive to *N. apis*. By contrast, 30% of the colonies that received FUM
138 (Fumidil-B®) were negative for *Nosema* spp.

139 These results suggest that none of the products tested were effective under our experimental
140 conditions. However, it is worth noting that the low consumption of the different doses of
141 treatment in the colonies, mainly in autumn, may have had a strong influence on the results
142 obtained. It has been shown previously that fumagillin administration is negatively correlated
143 with the proportion of bees infected in a colony (Higes et al., 2011; Botías et al., 2012b), which
144 also occurred to some extent in this study. A similar effect might have occurred with the other

145 therapeutic agents tested yet it may have been masked by the incorrect consumption of the
146 products applied, highlighting the importance of this issue and emphasizing that this should be
147 evaluated in studies to test therapeutic treatments of honey bee colonies. As such, it is
148 important to take into consideration factors that may interfere with therapeutic consumption,
149 as for instance the meteorological conditions at the moment of application, the attractive
150 presentation of the product for the bees, or its solubility in the selected excipient, all of which
151 may be of crucial importance. In this sense, studies into the optimal posology of potential
152 therapeutic agents to control nosemosis are particularly important, and this study represents a
153 preliminary step that should be complemented by further research. Furthermore, when
154 selecting an optimal posology it is important to adapt the preparation and the application of
155 the treatments to beekeepers real working conditions (*e.g.* type of hives, zootechnical
156 characteristics of the apiaries, etc...: Garrido-Bailón, 2012).

157 The effectiveness of these products was evaluated by assessing the *Nosema* spp. presence in a
158 composite sample of forager bees ($n \geq 50$) before and after treatment application. Given that
159 analysing the percentage of forager bees infected by *Nosema* was previously demonstrated to
160 be a more accurate method to estimate the level of infection in honey bee colonies, and thus,
161 to evaluate the effectiveness of an active molecule (Higes et al., 2008; Oliver, 2011; Botías et
162 al., 2012a; Goblirsch et al, 2013), this method should be utilized to examine the true
163 therapeutic capacity of these products in future studies.

164 In this assay, the adult bee population size, the amount of brood and the honey production
165 were monitored given that earlier studies have demonstrated that infection by *Nosema* spp.
166 can produce variations in these parameters (Fries, 1984; Yücel and Dogarglu, 2005; Higes et al.,
167 2008; Soroker et al., 2011; Botías et al., 2012a). In this regard, the adult bee population
168 remained similar between the groups throughout the study, with no significant differences in
169 the mean population values, except in June 2009 when colonies in the group FUM showed a

170 significantly increase in the population size as opposed to group C (ANOVA, $p = 0.037$; Figure
171 1). As for the number of brood cells, no differences were found between the groups
172 throughout the study ($p > 0.05$; Figure 2). The absence of significant alterations in the adult
173 bee population and the brood production between the control group (group C) and those that
174 received the products tested (groups NOS, SAL and VIT), may indicate a similar level of *Nosema*
175 infection in all the groups, as described elsewhere (Higes et al., 2008; Soroker et al., 2011;
176 Botías et al., 2013). Only the colonies treated with fumagillin (group FUM) showed a
177 significantly larger adult bee population than the control colonies at the moment of highest
178 colony activity (June 2009), which could reflect the stronger effect of this molecule in
179 controlling nosemosis than that of the other treatments. Fumagillin has previously been shown
180 to effectively control *N. ceranae* and *N. apis* infection (Gregorc and Sulimanovic, 1996; Higes et
181 al., 2008, 2011; Williams et al., 2008). However, in this study only 30% of the colonies treated
182 with fumagillin did not appear to be infected with *Nosema* spp., this value notably lower than
183 that achieved elsewhere (Higes et al., 2011; Botías et al., 2013). As fumagillin was not
184 consumed properly in autumn, a large quantity of the product remained in the hive for some
185 days, with the possibility that the molecule was degraded or diluted, thereby declining the
186 effective concentration possibly to levels below that required to control *Nosema* infection in
187 honey bees (Huang et al., 2013). Alternatively, as all the colonies remained infected with
188 *Nosema* during winter, maybe the colonies contained a high proportion of infected bees and
189 the treatment administered was insufficient to eliminate the parasite, as reported in a
190 previous study (Botías et al., 2013).

191 With regards honey production, the FUM group produced more honey (18.7 ± 5.6 kg/colony)
192 than the other groups, these differences being significant when comparing with the VIT ($11.5 \pm$
193 6.5 kg/colony; Mann-Whitney test, $U=10$, $p=0.037$) and C groups (12.3 ± 7.9 kg/colony; Mann-
194 Whitney test, $U=9$, $p=0.011$; Figure 3). The NOS treated colonies (14.4 ± 5.3 kg/colony) and the
195 SAL group (14.02 ± 7.7 kg/colony) did not show any significant differences to the other groups

196 in terms of honey production. This result may reflect the weaker infection following FUM
197 administration, as evident elsewhere (Botías et al., 2013), although again, as the percentage of
198 infected bees was not evaluated this hypothesis could not be corroborated. In the case of
199 Vitafeed Gold®, the method of application did not allow the consumption to be evaluated and
200 thus, we could not objectively analyze its capacity as a therapeutic agent to treat nosemosis.

201 For the time being, several alternative products and methods to that of fumagillin
202 administration have been evaluated as treatments to control nosemosis, for instance ApiHerb®
203 (Giacomelli et al., 2009; Nanetti, 2009), Nonosz® (Békési y col., 2009), or lysozymes of animal
204 origin and essential oils extracted from *Vetiveria zizanioides* (Maistrello et al., 2008). Of all the
205 molecules tested, Nozevit® has been seen to diminish the amount of *Nosema* spores in the
206 infected colonies. In addition, this compound induces the production and secretion of mucous
207 from the epithelial layer of treated bees that coats the peritrophic membrane, forming a firm
208 and resilient envelope that offers protection against new invasion with *Nosema* spp. spores, as
209 well as from other normal physiological processes (Tlak Gagjer et al., 2009, 2011). On the other
210 hand resveratrol (a natural phytoalexin: trans-3,5,4'-trihydroxystilbene) and thymol (terpen; 2-
211 iso propyl-5-methylphenol) also appear to be capable of diminishing the level of infection, and
212 thus, the mortality of experimentally infected bees (Maistrello et al., 2008; Costa et al., 2010).
213 In addition, the use of bacterial metabolites (surfactin; Porrini et al., 2010) or of double
214 stranded RNA (dsRNA) homologous to the genes that encode the ADP/ATP complex (Paldi et
215 al., 2010) to some extent inhibits the proliferation and development of *N. ceranae* in
216 experimentally infected bees. However, despite being promising alternatives to the use of
217 fumagillin, all these treatments require their effectiveness to be confirmed in field conditions.
218 Moreover, studies into the excipients and methods most appropriate for the application of
219 these compounds are necessary.

220 In the light of the high prevalence and the severe pathogenic action of *Nosema spp.*, and due
221 to the absence of authorized treatments to control these microsporidia in the EU, studies into
222 the effectiveness of potential therapeutic agents to combat this dangerous disease are
223 essential to restrain its widespread dispersal, and to provide appropriate solutions to the
224 beekeeping sector.

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231 **Conflict of interests**

232 None of the authors have any financial or personal relationships that could inappropriately
233 influence or bias the content of the paper. Trademarks are mentioned for scientific purposes
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- 332 population levels of workers and honey production on consecutive years. Pakistan Journal of
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1 Table 1. Experimental groups of the colonies, products, doses and posology at the time of
 2 application.

3

50 EXPERIMENTAL COLONIES					
GROUP	No. COLONIES	PRODUCT	CONCENTRATIO N APPLIED DOSE (MIX)	POSOLOGY	MOMENT OF APPLICATION
FUM	10	FUMIDIL-B® (Fumagillin 2%)	6 g./1 L. syrup	250 ml. mix/dose 1 dose per week during 4 weeks (total = 1 L./colony)	NOVEMBER 08/ APRIL 09
NOS	10	NOSESTAT® (a.m. Iodine 4 g. – Formic Acid 5 g. in 100 ml. of product)	3.75 ml./1 L. syrup	250 ml. mix/dose 3 doses distributed in 3 alternate days (total = 750 ml./colony)	NOVEMBER 08/ APRIL 09
SAL	10	PHENYL SALICYLATE	18 g./1 L. syrup	250 ml. mix/dose 1 dose per week during 4 weeks (total = 1 L./colony)	NOVEMBER 08/ APRIL 09
VIT	10	VITAFEED GOLD® (extract of <i>Beta vulgaris</i>)	100 g. /1 L. syrup	100 ml. mix/dose 5 doses, applying each one every other day (total = 500 ml./colony)	NOV.-DEC. 08/ APR.-MAY 09
C	10	SYRUP	Sugar-Water 1:1	250 ml. syrup/dose 1 dose per week during 4 weeks (total = 1 L./colony)	NOVEMBER 08/ APRIL 09

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8 Table 2. Mean consumption (%) of the potential therapeutic agents applied to the colonies
9 (s.d. = standard deviation).

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GROUP	CONSUMPTION (% applied dose \pm s.d.)	
	AUTUMN '08	SPRING '09
FUM	52.2 \pm 15.7 %	100%
NOS	36.7 \pm 14.4 %	100%
SAL	38.7 \pm 22.5 %	77.5 \pm 20.7 %
C	70 \pm 26.2 %	100%

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1 Figure 1. Average number of bee combs per group and per month.

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22 Figure 2. Average number of brood cells per group and per month.

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37 Figure 3. Average honey production (kg) per group upon harvesting (September 2008).

38 Asterisks mark the significant differences between groups ($P < 0.05$).

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